

Mechanical properties of carbon/bismaleimide unidirectional and angle-ply laminates

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SUMMARY: In the present study, mechanical properties of a heat-resistant CFRP, G40-800/5260, carbon/bismaleimide system are investigated experimentally. Laminate configurations are unidirectional $[0]_5$ and angle-ply $[30/-30]_s$, $[45/-45]_s$, $[60/-60]_s$ laminates. On- and off-axis tensile tests are performed on the unidirectional laminates. Tensile tests are conducted on the angle-ply laminates. The specimen size was 150mm long and 10mm wide. In order to investigate the effect of temperature on the mechanical properties, the tests are performed at the room temperature and 100°C. The temperature dependence of the mechanical properties is discussed. To model the nonlinearity in the stress-strain behavior of the unidirectional laminates, the one-parameter plasticity model is used. The effective stress-effective plastic strain curves are obtained for unidirectional laminates at room temperature and 100°C. It is found that the curves gathered on one master curve at each temperature which proves that the one-parameter plasticity model is valid for this material system. An attempt is also made to combine the one-parameter plasticity model and the classical lamination theory to predict the stress-strain relation of the angle-ply laminates.

Keywords: mechanical properties, carbon/bismaleimide, unidirectional laminate, angle-ply laminate, heat resistant CFRP

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the heat resistant CFRPs which are considered for the application in the aerospace have been developed. Since the matrix properties are significantly influenced by temperature, it is important to examine the temperature dependence of CFRP off-axis properties. In the present study, mechanical properties of a heat-resistant CFRP, G40-800/5260, carbon/bismaleimide system are investigated experimentally. On- and off-axis tensile tests are performed on the unidirectional laminates. Tensile tests are conducted on the angle-ply laminates. The tests are performed at the room temperature and 100°C. To model the nonlinearity in the stress-strain behavior of the unidirectional laminates, the one-parameter plasticity model [1] is used. The parameter is determined to give the master effective stress-effective plastic strain curve at room temperature and 100°C. A combination of the one-parameter plasticity model and the classical lamination theory is performed to predict the stress-strain relation of the angle-ply laminates. The comparison between the prediction and the experimental results shows a reasonable agreement.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A material system used is G40-800/5260 carbon/bismaleimide heat resistant CFRP. Laminate configurations are unidirectional $[0]_5$ and angle-ply $[30/-30]_s$, $[45/-45]_s$, $[60/-60]_s$ laminates. On- and off-axis tensile tests are performed on the unidirectional laminates. The off-axis angles are 15°, 30°, 45° and 60°. Tensile tests are conducted on the angle-ply laminates. The specimen size was 150mm long and 10mm wide. In order to investigate the effect of temperature on the mechanical properties, the tests are performed at the room temperature and 100°C. Specimen configuration is shown in Fig.1. A biaxial strain gage is mounted at the center of each specimen to measure both the longitudinal and transverse strains. The crosshead speed is 0.5mm/min.

Fig.1 Specimen configuration

RESULTS

Figure 2 shows experimentally-obtained stress-strain curves for unidirectional laminates at (a) room temperature and (b) 100°C. At both room temperature and 100°C, the stress-strain curves in 0° and 90° directions are almost linear. However, nonlinear behavior is seen in the stress-strain curves of off-axis specimens. As temperature increases, Young's modulus decreases and the nonlinearity increases.

Figure 3 shows stress-strain curves for angle-ply laminates at (a) room temperature and (b) 100°C. As seen in the unidirectional laminates, the nonlinearity in the stress-strain curves is enhanced at higher temperature.

Fig.2 Stress-strain curves for unidirectional laminates ((a) Room Temperature and (b) 100°C)

Fig.3 Stress-strain curves for angle-ply laminates ((a) Room Temperature and (b) 100°C)

ANALYTICAL PROCEDURE

General 2-D Plasticity Model

A yield function that is quadratic in stress is assumed for the general 3-D fiber composite as

$$\begin{aligned}
 2f(\sigma_{ij}) = & a_{11}\sigma_{11}^2 + a_{22}\sigma_{22}^2 + a_{33}\sigma_{33}^2 \\
 & + 2a_{12}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 2a_{13}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{33} + 2a_{23}\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33} \\
 & + 2a_{44}\sigma_{23}^2 + 2a_{55}\sigma_{13}^2 + 2a_{66}\sigma_{12}^2 = k
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where k is a state variable and the stresses σ_{ij} refer to the stresses in the principal material directions. By using the associated flow rule, the yield function is taken as the plastic potential function from which the incremental plastic strain can be derived as

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} d\lambda \quad (2)$$

where superscript p denotes plasticity, and $d\lambda$ is a proportionality factor. The increment of plastic work per unit volume is given by

$$dW^p = \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = 2fd\lambda \quad (3)$$

Let the effective stress be defined as

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sqrt{3f} \quad (4)$$

The effective plastic strain increment can be defined such that

$$dW^p = \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \bar{\sigma} d\bar{\varepsilon}^p \quad (5)$$

Substitution of (3) and (4) into (5) yields

$$d\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \frac{2}{3} \bar{\sigma} d\lambda \quad (6)$$

and

$$d\lambda = \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{\varepsilon}^p}{d\bar{\sigma}} \right) \left(\frac{d\bar{\sigma}}{\bar{\sigma}} \right) \quad (7)$$

Consider a state of plane stress parallel to the x_1 - x_2 plane. The plastic potential function reduces to

$$2f = a_{11}\sigma_{11}^2 + a_{22}\sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{12}\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 2a_{66}\sigma_{12}^2 \quad (8)$$

From (2) and (8), the plastic strain increments are obtained as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{11}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{22}^p \\ d\gamma_{12}^p \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & 0 \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} d\lambda \quad (9)$$

Off-Axis Tension Test

The complete orthotropic plastic flow rule is defined if the parameters a_{11} , a_{22} , a_{12} , a_{66} and $d\lambda$ are determined. To determine $d\lambda$, the effective stress-effective plastic strain relation must be established. This can be accomplished from the results of tension tests on off-axis specimens.

Let the x -axis be the uniaxial loading direction which makes an angle θ with the fiber direction x_1 -axis. This stresses referring to the material principal directions (x_1 and x_2) are related to the applied uniaxial stress σ_x as

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{11} = \sigma_x \cos^2 \theta \\ \sigma_{22} = \sigma_x \sin^2 \theta \\ \sigma_{12} = -\sigma_x \sin \theta \cos \theta \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Substitution of (10) into (8) and (4) yields

$$\bar{\sigma} = h(\theta)\sigma_x \quad (11)$$

where

$$h(\theta) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \{ a_{11} \cos^4 \theta + a_{22} \sin^4 \theta + 2(a_{12} + a_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \}} \quad (12)$$

Using the coordinate transformation law for strains, the plastic strain increment in the loading direction is given by

$$d\varepsilon_x^p = d\varepsilon_{11}^p \cos^2 \theta + d\varepsilon_{22}^p \sin^2 \theta - d\gamma_{12}^p \sin \theta \cos \theta \quad (13)$$

Substituting (9) into (13) and using the relations (10), (11) and (6), the following relation can be derived.

$$d\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \frac{d\varepsilon_x^p}{h(\theta)} \quad (14)$$

For monotonic loading, the above equation is integrable. Thus,

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \frac{\varepsilon_x^p}{h(\theta)} \quad (15)$$

The relation between the effective stress and effective plastic strain can now be obtained by the experimentally obtained uniaxial stress and plastic strain. Since the effective stress-effective plastic strain curve should be unique in monotonic loading for a given material, the parameters a_{11} , a_{22} , a_{12}

and a_{66} must be chosen so that the resulting effective stress-effective plastic strain relations is independent of θ . It can also be shown that the plastic Poisson's ratio defined by the following equation can be expressed by the plasticity parameters and loading angles as

$$v_{\theta}^p \equiv -\frac{d\varepsilon_y^p}{d\varepsilon_x^p} = -\frac{(a_{11} + a_{22} - 2a_{66})\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + a_{12}(\sin^4 \theta + \cos^4 \theta)}{a_{11} \cos^4 \theta + a_{22} \sin^4 \theta + 2(a_{12} + a_{66})\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta} \quad (16)$$

DISCUSSION

Plasticity Analysis for the Unidirectional Laminates

To model the nonlinear stress-strain relation of the unidirectional laminates, the one-parameter plasticity model proposed by Sun and Chen is applied [1]. Following the procedure in Ref. [1], it is assumed that the strains can be divided into two parts, that is, linear elastic and nonlinear parts.

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^e + \varepsilon^p \quad (17)$$

where superscripts e and p denote linear elasticity and nonlinearity, respectively.

It is also assumed that the nonlinear part comes from plasticity. In one-parameter plasticity model, we aim to obtain a parameter which lead to a master curve of the effective stress-effective plastic strain curve from the data of all angles.

Figure 4 shows the relation between the plastic strain and the uniaxial stress. In Table 1, Young's moduli which are used to determine the linear strain are listed. Figure 5 show the resulting effective stress-effective plastic strain curves. It is seen that a master curve of the effective stress-effective plastic strain relation is obtained at each temperature. The plasticity parameter used to obtain the effective stress-effective plastic strain curves are listed in Table 2. The master curves of the effective stress-effective plastic strain curves are fitted in the form

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \alpha \bar{\sigma}^n \quad (18)$$

The fitting parameters are listed in Table 3.

Table1 Young's module for unidirectional laminates of each angle

	0°	15°	30°	45°	60°	90°
R.T.	159.4	58.0	23.8	17.3	12.1	11.8
100°C	160.8	35.2	21.2	13.0	12.9	8.70

(a) Room Temperature

(b) 100°C

Fig.4 Relation between plastic strain and stress

Table2 Plasticity parameter

	a_{66}
R.T.	1.36
100°C	2.54

Fig.5 Effective stress-effective strain curves for unidirectional laminates (room temperature and 100°C)

Table3 Fitting parameters

	α (MPa $^{-n}$)	n
R.T.	3.0×10^{-12}	4.2
100°C	3.6×10^{-11}	4.8

Prediction of Stress-Strain Curves for Angle-Ply Laminates

In the present study, an attempt is made to predict the nonlinear behavior of angle-ply laminates under an assumption that the nonlinear behavior of the unidirectional composite is known, that is, the nonlinear behavior of unidirectional laminate can be described by the Sun and Chen one-parameter plasticity model. We perform a classical lamination analysis using the one-parameter plasticity model [2].

The total strain increments are assumed to be the sum of the elastic strain increments and the plastic strain increments. The elastic strain increments obey the orthotropic stress-strain relations. The total incremental stress-strain relations for the elastic-plastic composite can be expressed in the form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{11} \\ d\varepsilon_{22} \\ d\gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{16} \\ S_{21} & S_{22} & S_{26} \\ S_{61} & S_{62} & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} d\sigma_{11} \\ d\sigma_{22} \\ d\sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} S_{11} = \frac{1}{E_1}, S_{12} = S_{21} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1}, S_{16} = S_{61} = 0 \\ S_{22} = \frac{1}{E_2} + \Omega\sigma_{22}^2, S_{26} = S_{62} = 2a_{66}\Omega\sigma_{12}\sigma_{22} \\ S_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}} + 4a_{66}^2\Omega\sigma_{12}^2, \Omega = \frac{9}{4}\alpha n\bar{\sigma}^{n-3} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Now a multidirectional laminate under in-plane loading is considered. The total incremental stress-strain relations for the k th lamina in the laminate can be expressed in the form in the material (local) coordinate system

$$\{d\varepsilon^k\} = [S(\sigma^k)]\{d\sigma^k\} \quad (21)$$

where superscript k denotes k th lamina. In the global coordinate system,

$$\{d\tilde{\varepsilon}^k\} = [\tilde{S}(\sigma^k)]\{d\tilde{\sigma}^k\} \quad (22)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \{d\varepsilon^k\} = [T_\varepsilon]\{d\tilde{\varepsilon}^k\} \\ \{d\sigma^k\} = [T_\sigma]\{d\tilde{\sigma}^k\} \\ [\tilde{S}(\sigma^k)] = [T_\varepsilon]^{-1}[S(\sigma^k)][T_\sigma] \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

$[T_\sigma]$ and $[T_\varepsilon]$ are coordinate transformation matrix for stress and strain, respectively. The relations between laminate stress and strain and the ply stress and strain in the global coordinate system are

$$\{\varepsilon^{LAM}\} = \{\tilde{\varepsilon}^k\} \quad (24)$$

$$\{\sigma^{LAM}\} = \frac{\sum t_k \{\tilde{\sigma}^k\}}{\sum t_k} \quad (25)$$

where the superscript LAM represents the multidirectional laminate and t_k is the thickness of the k th ply. Considering the above relations, the stress strain behavior of a multidirectional laminate under in-plane loading can be obtained in a step by step manner.

Figure 7 shows the comparison between the experimental results and the analytical predictions for stress-strain curves of the angle-ply laminates. A reasonable agreement is obtained which implies the validity of the combination of the one-parameter plasticity model and the classical lamination theory. It may be possible to predict the stress-strain behavior of general multidirectional laminates by using the one-parameter plasticity model.

Fig.7 Stress-strain curves for angle-ply laminates. Comparison between the analytical prediction and the experimental results.

CONCLUSIONS

Nonlinear mechanical behavior of heat resistant carbon/bismaleimide unidirectional and angle-ply laminates under uniaxial tensile loading is investigated experimentally. The effects of temperature on the mechanical properties are also discussed. The one-parameter plasticity model is used to characterize the nonlinear behavior of the unidirectional laminates. By combining the one-parameter plasticity model with the classical lamination theory, the mechanical behavior of the angle-ply laminates is predicted and reasonable agreement with experimental results is obtained. As a lamina-level macroscopic approach, the one-parameter plasticity model will be useful to predict the mechanical behavior of multidirectional laminates.

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